

HAPPINESS AT WORK AS PERCEIVED BY THE MILLENNIAL EMPLOYEES IN A MANUFACTURING COMPANY IN LAGUNA: BASIS FOR RETENTION PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the factors affecting happiness at work and the retention among millennial employees in a manufacturing company in Laguna. Millennials are individuals born between the early 1980s and the mid-1990's to early 2000s. This generational cohort spans from approximately 18 to 42 years of age. Also known as Generation Y. Utilizing structured questionnaires, a total of 326 participants rated the importance of various factors on a Likert scale. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean). Understanding the factors that contribute to job satisfaction is essential for organizations to retain talent, enhance productivity, save costs, and create a positive work environment. It's a critical component of effective human resource management and can lead to better organizational performance and success. The findings highlighted several significant factors that influenced job satisfaction. Furthermore, the study analyzed the significance of happiness variables with the Herzberg 2-factor principle. The summarized data revealed a high level of importance in almost all factors contributing to employee happiness. However, the most emphasized factor was salary and benefits, achieving an overall average score of 4.83. Findings also highlighted the bottom two factors, good relationships and work-life balance, as the least important indicators of happiness at work as perceived by the millennials. In the light of these findings, the researcher recommended retention programs that will encompass various areas to be adopted by the manufacturing industry.

Keywords: *Job satisfaction, Retention, Millennial, Employees, Quantitative*

INTRODUCTION

The millennial generation, the largest generation in the workforce, possesses attitudes, values, beliefs, and aspirations that are distinct from those of previous generations, necessitating a deeper comprehension of their motivations and work preferences. Millennials value meaningful and engaging employment, as well as a simple work process. When confronted with difficulty or a lack of recognition, they are more likely to resign or lose focus, which could result in absenteeism or errors. According to the Pew Research Center (2015), a significant proportion of millennials have departed their employers within the first three years of employment. The retention and motivation of this cohort has become a top priority for human resource professionals (Ertas, 2015). The employees of today are more proactive and opportunistic in their career decisions, readily switching positions when dissatisfied with their current employer or position. The attrition of millennials incurs expenses for separation, replacement, and training for organizations (Deery & Jago, 2014). According to Harris-Boundy and Flatt (2010), scholarly interest in the Millennial Generation has increased as they enter the workforce. Others argue that millennials are ambitious, value organizational training and development, prefer meaningful work, and pursue personal fulfillment at work (Hauw & Vos, 2010). Despite the focus on millennials, there is a lack of research on the workplace factors that influence their organizational commitment. Therefore, it is essential for organizations to consider workplace characteristics that encourage millennials' long-term commitment.

This study identified the happiness variables that contribute to happiness at work and organizational commitment among millennials, such as salaries and benefits, management and leadership style, work and life balance, good relationship, company image and culture, training and growth, career opportunity, work/job itself, recognition and reward. It also determined the level of importance of hygiene and motivation factors to the millennial employees' happiness at work and to develop applicable HR retention programs to address the increasing turnover rate within the organization. By focusing on millennial employees at Furukawa Electric Autoparts Phils. Inc (FEAP, Inc), this investigation analyzed the factors influencing happiness in the workplace and the retention of the millennial employees in order to provide insights to help the company to retain and motivate them.

Research Questions and Objectives

The study aimed to comprehensively assess workplace happiness among millennials in the manufacturing industry, guided by Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene theory. It focused on identifying motivational and hygiene factors affecting job satisfaction and overall well-being. To fulfill these goals, the study was designed to:

1. It identified the factors contributing to millennials' workplace happiness, including hygiene factors (e.g., salaries, management style, work-life balance, relationships, company culture) and motivational factors (e.g., training, career opportunities, job nature, recognition, and rewards).

2. It determined the most and least significant indicators of workplace happiness, as perceived by millennials.
3. The study provided retention programs aimed at managing staff turnover rates within a manufacturing company, with the goal of keeping turnover below a specified attrition rate of 3% and retaining valuable millennial talent.

Theoretical Framework

Frederick Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory, also known as the Motivator-Hygiene Theory, was deemed relevant to this research. This theory aims to explain job satisfaction and motivation in the workplace by proposing that satisfaction and dissatisfaction stem from different factors.

Figure 1: Herzberg's Two-Factor Principles

Conceptual Framework

From the study's theoretical frameworks, the researcher developed the conceptual framework of the study. Figure 3. Conceptual Framework illustrating the Variables on Employee Level of Happiness and Retention to develop Human Resource Strategy

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework

The conceptual diagram applies Herzberg's theory to categorize factors as hygiene (extrinsic) and motivation (intrinsic) to enhance employee happiness and retention. Survey data quantified their impact, informing tailored HR programs, aligning needs with values for enhanced success

Significance of the Study

The results of the study will be of great benefit to the following:

Theory. This study underscores the significance of Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene theory (1959) concerning job satisfaction and retention within a millennial workforce, particularly in a private institution. The alignment of this theory with the study allows for a comprehensive exploration of the interplay between motivational and hygiene factors in the context of happiness at work and retention among millennial employees within a private institution.

Practice. Gaining insight into the factors influencing the millennials' organizational commitment and workplace happiness may equip HR professionals with the knowledge needed to tailor their recruitment, retention, and engagement strategies to suit the preferences and needs of this generation.

Policy. Beyond its academic contributions, this study provides a practical tool for local stakeholders in companies to develop organization-wide strategies for enhancing development and retention efforts targeted at millennials. This insight is not only applicable to the specific company under study but can also offer guidance to other businesses in the same industry grappling with their retention challenges.

Social Actions. This study adds value by contributing to the knowledge base for students, future researchers, and readers interested in Hygiene & Motivation Factors for Millennial Employees in manufacturing. It offers a foundation for further research, enriching academic curricula, and preparing individuals for the job market. Additionally, it guides organizational leaders in enhancing retention, creating engaging programs, and fostering a positive work environment, benefiting both employees and the organization.

Scope and Delimitations

The study is limited to one company only, focused on workplace happiness and retention factors among millennial employees. It profiles demographic characteristics such as age, gender, civil status, education, and tenure. However, it had limitations: it relied primarily on a descriptive survey method, used self-administered questionnaires that could introduce bias, and didn't consider external factors like economic conditions or industry trends. The study distributed 326 questionnaires across company departments, excluding Japanese officers and local managers due to their job roles. These limitations defined the study's scope and clarified the context and population of interest.

Definition of Terms

The following terms were operationally defined as used in the study.

Attrition. This refers to the loss of valuable employees, especially those with unique skills or expertise, from an organization.

Benefits. They refer to non-wage compensation provided to employees in addition to their normal wages or salaries.

Employee Turnover. This refers to human resources and workforce management metric that measures the rate at which employees leave an organization and are replaced by new employees. It is typically expressed as a percentage and is calculated over a specific period, such as a month, quarter, or year.

Hygiene Factors. These refer to extrinsic elements or conditions in the workplace that, when absent or deficient, can lead to job dissatisfaction and decreased motivation among employees. These factors were first introduced by Frederick Herzberg as part of his two-factor theory of job satisfaction and motivation, also known as the Motivation-Hygiene theory.

Job Satisfaction. This refers to the level of contentment, fulfillment, or happiness that individuals derive from their jobs or work experiences

Millennials. These refer to individuals born between the early 1980s and the mid-1990's to early 2000s. This generational cohort spans from approximately 18 to 42 years of age. Also known as Generation Y.

Motivational Factors. These refer to elements or aspects that stimulate and drive individuals from within, inspiring them to take action, set and pursue goals, and engage in activities because they find them inherently rewarding.

Happiness at Work. This refers to the overall sense of contentment, fulfillment, and well-being that employees experience in their job or workplace.

Review of Pertinent Literatures

The two-factor theory of work motivation, developed by Herzberg, Mausner, and Snyderman in 1959, posits that job satisfaction and dissatisfaction are influenced by distinct sets of factors (Herzberg et al., 1959; Stello, 2011). Herzberg identified two categories of factors: motivation factors and hygiene factors (Robbins, 2010). Motivation factors are intrinsic to the job and contribute to job satisfaction, while hygiene factors are extrinsic and aim to prevent dissatisfaction. It is important to note that the presence of hygiene factors alone does not lead to job satisfaction; motivation factors must also be addressed to enhance employee performance (Robbins, 2010).

When employees' expectations towards the job are met, they lead to higher job satisfaction and can reduce turnover (Yang et al, 2012). Reducing turnover in the private institution has been a topic of discussion for quite some time, mentioning the need to retain talented employees since employee turnover has an impact on organizational performance (Deery & Jago, 2015). When the institution meets the job expectations, the individual experiences positive feelings, so, these positive emotions indicate job satisfaction. Employees that perceive their needs to be met have higher job satisfaction. With job satisfaction being one of the most important factors in organizational behavior, and an indicator of whether the employee has intentions to leave the job, or not (Sarwar & Abugre, 2013), it is important to find out how to engage the millennials and analyze their preferences in order to retain them (Deery & Jago, 2015).

According to Luthans (2011), five dimensions were formulated and had been extensively researched and used to measure job satisfaction over the years as "they represent the most important characteristics of a job about which employees have affective responses." They are the work itself, pay, promotion, co-workers, and supervision. Job satisfaction and turnover rates are highly correlated, the more satisfaction the less turnover rate. This indicates that when employees are not satisfied with their job, it leads higher turnover rates. Hence, lack of job satisfaction leads to higher turnover rates (Mullins, 2013). Employees with higher job satisfaction, are less likely to consider leaving the organization, and less likely to leave permanently (Bandura & Lyons, 2014). The retention of personnel is essential to staying competitive within an industry (Murphy, 2012). Due to the size of

the millennial generation, which is 76 million (Murphy, 2012), the retention of the millennial workforce is essential to the success of organizations. Millennials are leaving organizations before staying three years (U.S. Department of Labor, 2014), which can cause organizational issues with obtaining a return on the investment of millennials brought into the company.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive-survey method to systematically examine hygiene and motivation factors influencing job satisfaction and retention among millennial employees. This approach facilitated the organized collection and analysis of data, enabling a comprehensive illustration of these factors. The use of survey questionnaires, specifically self-administered ones prepared by the researcher, was the primary data collection method employed in the study.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in a multinational manufacturing company that is a renowned manufacturer of steering roll connectors (SRC) for car airbag system, where the researcher is currently employed. Participants in this study were employees from the company's different departments.

Population and Sampling Design

The researcher of this study employed a statistical formula to determine the appropriate sample size for the data collection and analysis needed to be conducted. It utilized 95% ($z=1.96$) confidence level, five percent (5%) margin of error and population size of 1758. The computation indicated that 326 participants were the needed sample.

Research Instrument

The researcher developed a two-section survey questionnaire based on existing literature. The first section gathered demographic data (e.g., name, age, gender), while the second section assessed happiness factors (e.g., salaries, leadership style). The questionnaire aimed to evaluate happiness's impact on employee satisfaction and retention. Respondents used a 5-point Likert Scale.

Data Gathering Procedure

The research focused on millennial employees at a selected manufacturing company in Laguna Technopark. Data collection involved distributing 326 questionnaires to these employees, with management approval. After retrieving the completed questionnaires, results were tabulated based on response frequencies and then interpreted using statistical tools to address research questions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part plays a crucial role as a link between raw data and informed decision-making. It encapsulates the essence of the research, offering a comprehensive and enlightening overview of the findings. By meticulously presenting the data and conducting thoughtful analysis, it equips decision-makers with the knowledge and insights necessary to make informed choices and drive positive outcomes within the organization.

1. The Level of Importance of the Motivation and Hygiene Factors as Perceived by the Millennials in Contributing to their Happiness at Work, using Herzberg 2- Factor Principle.

The data, which had been meticulously presented in Table 1, served as a vivid panorama, offering a lucid and insightful portrayal of how each factor had been perceived in terms of its significance, as indicated by the grand mean scores. These grand mean scores had functioned as the compass that guided the understanding, with the highest-ranked factors having emerged as paramount in the eyes of the respondents. Eminently, the factor of salaries and benefits had taken the spotlight, with its grand mean score standing resolutely at an impressive 4.83. This resounding score unequivocally underscored its exceptional importance, signifying that it had been held in the highest regard by respondents.

It resonated as an unequivocally crucial and supremely vital component in retaining millennial employees. Conversely, the factors of good relationship (4.65 Mean) and work and life balance (4.61 Mean), as delineated by the data, had found themselves at the opposite end of the spectrum. Here, the grand mean scores suggested a different narrative, portraying these factors as the least important within the context of employee retention. This perspective, gleaned from the data, had provided a contrasting viewpoint, shedding light on the aspects that had required further attention and strategic consideration in the pursuit of retaining millennial talent.

Table No. 1: Summary Result of Workplace Happiness Variables

Happiness Variable	% rating for NI	% for rating for SI	% rating for MI	% rating for I	% rating for VI	Grand Mean	Ranking	Description
<i>Salaries and Benefits</i>	0.08%	0%	1.38%	13.27%	84.06%	4.83	1	Very Important
<i>Career Opportunity</i>	0.23%	0.31%	1.23%	19.92%	78.31%	4.76	2	Very Important
<i>Training and Growth</i>	0.31%	0.41%	2.46%	18.77%	78.82%	4.74	3	Very Important
<i>Management & Leadership Style</i>	0.05%	0.15%	2.15%	25.33%	72.32%	4.69	4	Very Important
<i>Company Image and culture</i>	0.25%	0.37%	2.12%	25.12%	71.94%	4.67	5.5	Very Important
<i>Work/Job Itself</i>	0.06%	0.06%	2.32%	27.12%	69.44%	4.67	5.5	Very Important
<i>Recognition and Reward</i>	0.10%	0.62%	3.18%	25.44%	70.00%	4.66	6	Very Important
<i>Good Relationship</i>	0.15%	0.69%	2.43%	26.65%	70.83%	4.65	7	Very Important
<i>Work and Life Balance</i>	0.74%	1.35%	4.35%	22.63%	70.20%	4.61	8	Very Important
OVER-ALL RATING						4.7		Very Important

*NI= Not Important, SI= Slightly Important, MI= Moderately Important, I= Important, VI= Very Important.

2. The Most and Least Important Indicators of Happiness at Work as Perceived by the Millennials

Table 2 thoughtfully summarized the most and least significant indicators of workplace happiness as perceived by millennials. This presentation format was chosen for clarity and organization, allowing readers to quickly identify the factors that had the most and least influence on workplace happiness within this demographic. By connecting these findings with Herzberg's theory, the researcher provided a deeper and more nuanced insight into the factors that had affected millennials' job satisfaction and engagement in the workplace.

Summary of Results in the Hygiene Factors

The overall score for the hygiene factors, encompassing all the dimensions and factors assessed, was 4.7, as indicated in Table 16. This score signified that these hygiene factors had been considered extremely important by the employees, as reflected in the average score. The individual scores for each dimension and factor had collectively contributed to this overall assessment. Notably, the factor of salary and benefits had received the highest grand mean of 4.83, underlining its exceptional importance in the context of employee perceptions of workplace happiness. Conversely, the factors of good relationship (4.65 Mean) and work and life balance (4.61 Mean), as delineated by the data, had found themselves at the opposite end of the spectrum.

Table No. 2: Summary of Happiness Variable – Hygiene Factors

Happiness Variable- Hygiene Factors	Grand Mean	Description	Ranking
<i>Salaries and Benefits</i>	4.83	Very Important	1
<i>Management & Leadership Style</i>	4.69	Very Important	2
<i>Company Image and culture</i>	4.67	Very Important	3
<i>Good Relationship</i>	4.65	Very Important	4
<i>Work and Life Balance</i>	4.61	Very Important	5
OVER-ALL RATING	4.7	Very Important	

**The rankings are arranged from highest to lowest. 1 is the highest grand mean and 5 being the lowest.*

Summary of Results- Motivating Factors

Based on the findings presented in table 3, Recognition and Reward held the fourth position in the ranking, with a relatively lower grand mean score of 4.66. This indicated that, among the various factors assessed, recognition and reward had been perceived as

having somewhat less significance according to the respondents' perspectives. It was evident that other motivating factors might have taken precedence over this dimension in their assessment of workplace motivation. The Work/Job Itself dimension claimed the third (3rd) position in the ranking' characterized by a commendable grand mean score of 4.67. This dimension was centered on the fundamental concept that employees had a strong desire to feel that their job roles involved making meaningful contributions that extended beyond their personal scope. Career Opportunity secured the top spot, ranking first (1st) with an impressive grand mean score of 4.76. This dimension emerged as a highly significant factor considered by employees in their decision to stay with an organization.

Table No. 3: Summary of Motivating Factors

Happiness Variables- Motivating Factors	Grand Mean	Description	Ranking
<i>Career Opportunity</i>	4.76	Very Important	1
<i>Training and Growth</i>	4.74	Very Important	2
<i>Work/Job Itself</i>	4.67	Very Important	3
<i>Recognition and Reward</i>	4.66	Very Important	4
OVER-ALL RATING	4.71	Very Important	

**The rankings are arranged from highest to the lowest. 1 is the highest grand mean and 4 being the lowest.*

3. Strategies and Intervention to Improve the Retention Rate of The Millennial Employees in Manufacturing Industry

To enhance the retention of millennial employees at FEAP Inc., it is recommended to implement various strategies addressing the important retention variables. Firstly, in terms of salaries and benefits, a review of the existing structures and the implementation of Performance Management Systems with rewards for deserving employees is advised. Secondly, work-life balance can be promoted by offering flexible working options and engaging employees through activities that support alignment and employee well-being. Thirdly, training and growth opportunities should be provided to improve leadership qualities, and regular assembly meetings can include a Work Appreciation Program to reinforce desired behaviors and workplace values. Effective management and leadership styles are also crucial, involving encouraging engagement, promoting professional relationships, providing clear directions, and building mutual trust and respect between

employees and management. Additionally, transparent and fair provisions of career development opportunities, along with mentoring programs, can enhance career prospects. Improving the work/job itself can be achieved through regular stress reduction programs and involving employees in continuous improvement initiatives. Fostering good relationships and teamwork contributes to a positive work environment, and recognizing and rewarding employee efforts through both monetary and non-monetary means can further motivate employees. Finally, promoting a company culture that values and respects employees as the organization's most important asset, involving key employees in reviewing the company's mission, vision, and values, can strengthen the company image and culture. It is recommended to evaluate the effectiveness of these recommendations to ensure continuous improvement in employee retention at FEAP Inc.

Summary of Findings

The study analyzed happiness factors affecting millennial employees at Furukawa Electric Autoparts Philippines Inc. through structured questionnaires from 326 participants. It encapsulates the essence of the research, offering a comprehensive and enlightening overview of the findings. Research indicates that both intrinsic and extrinsic factors affect job satisfaction and motivation. For instance, a study in Malaysia showed that the presence of extrinsic motivation positively impacted job satisfaction, while the absence of intrinsic motivation factors demotivated employees (Wan Fauziah & Tan, 2013). Similarly, in China, extrinsic motivation factors were found to take precedence over intrinsic factors in motivating employees to work diligently (Yang, 2012). Key findings: Salaries and benefits are vital (grand mean 4.83); management and leadership style matters (4.69); work-life balance is significant (4.61); positive workplace relationships are crucial (4.65); company culture is vital (4.67); job nature and conditions are influential (4.67); training and growth opportunities are essential (4.74); and career advancement matters (4.76). Salary and benefits are paramount, while good relationships (4.65) and work-life balance (4.61) are less critical for retention. Recommendations include revisiting compensation, fostering feedback, offering leadership training, promoting work-life balance, and recognizing employee contributions to enhance millennial retention at FEAP Inc.

Conclusions

Based on the indicated findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The mean ratings for each happiness factor, both hygiene and motivational, were consistently "Very Important" to millennials. This emphasizes their indispensable role in workplace happiness and employee commitment. While the results are positive, additional programs or interventions are needed to enhance employee retention, as the data clearly show the impact of these factors.
2. The results of the study confirmed that among all the indicators of happiness at work included in the questionnaire, the respondents were able to identify both the most and least important factors influencing their workplace satisfaction. The most important indicators of happiness at work, based on the data and research, are:

Salary, Compensation, and Benefits; Management and Leadership Style; Opportunities for Career Growth; Work-Life Balance; Effective Communication; Positive Work Relationships; Company Image and Culture. On the other hand, the 2 least important indicators, as per the data, are: Good Relationship & Work-Life Balance

3. The researcher provided recommendations for manufacturing companies to retain millennial talent and manage staff turnover. These recommendations cover aspects such as compensation, performance management, work-life balance, leadership development, effective management, career development, job-related factors, teamwork, recognition and rewards, and building a positive organizational culture.

Recommendations

This study had unveiled that happiness variables, as assessed through the

Herzberg 2-factor principle, indeed played a significant role in enhancing workplace happiness among millennial employees. Thus, the following recommendations were hereby presented:

- The researcher recommended that manufacturing companies implement the proposed strategies and retention programs to assess their impact on retention rates. This study and its methodologies can serve as a guide for other businesses in the same industry to analyze and address their own retention challenges.
- The study did not investigate the potential impact of external factors, such as economic conditions or industry-specific trends, on workplace happiness and millennial retention.
- The academic community and future researchers can leverage the study's findings to align educational and training programs with the competencies required by employers. This alignment prepares individuals, including students and job seekers, for employer expectations and fosters commitment and responsiveness in the workforce.
- It is recommended ensuring balanced gender representation in future studies to comprehensively analyze retention factors and strategies for both male and female millennial resulting in a more nuanced and comprehensive analysis of the research problem.
- Moreover, integrating qualitative research will yield valuable insights by exploring nuances, perspectives, and hidden patterns, enriching data through interviews, surveys, and observations, ultimately deepening and broadening the findings.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher complied with the basic standards of research ethics and also followed the Data Privacy Act in the collection and process of data gathered.

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